

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

O'zbekiston aholisi umr davomiyligi funksiyasini parametrik statistik modellar asosida baholash

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi aholisi umr davomiyligi funksiyasini parametrik statistik modellar asosida baholash masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotda umr davomiyligi musbat qiymatlarni qabul qiluvchi tasodifiy miqdor sifatida qaralib, rasmiy demografik ma'lumotlar asosida empirik umr davomiyligi funksiyasi quriladi. O'limlilik jarayonini tavsiflash maqsadida Gompertz hamda Weibull parametrik modellaridan foydalaniladi. Modellarining noma'lum parametrlarini baholashda haqiqatga maksimal o'xshashlik usuli qo'llaniladi. Olingan natijalar tanlangan parametrik modellar empirik umr davomiyligi funksiyasiga yetarli darajada yaxshi mos kelishini hamda o'limlilik jarayonining asosiy xususiyatlarini aniq aks ettirishini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari demografik tahlil, sug'urta va pensiya tizimlarini rejalashtirishda ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: umr davomiyligi, parametrik modellar, Gompertz modeli, Weibull modeli, demografik prognozlash

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы оценки функции продолжительности жизни населения Республики Узбекистан на основе параметрических статистических моделей. В исследовании продолжительность жизни трактуется как случайная величина, принимающая положительные значения, и на основе официальных демографических данных строится эмпирическая функция выживания. Для описания процесса смертности используются параметрические модели Гомпертца и Вейбулла. Оценивание неизвестных параметров моделей осуществляется с применением метода максимального правдоподобия. Полученные результаты показывают, что выбранные параметрические модели обеспечивают достаточно хорошее приближение эмпирической функции продолжительности жизни и адекватно отражают основные особенности процесса смертности. Результаты исследования имеют научно-практическое значение для демографического анализа, а также для планирования систем страхования и пенсионного обеспечения.

Ключевые слова: продолжительность жизни, параметрические модели, модель Гомпертца, модель Вейбулла, демографическое прогнозирование.

Abstract: This article addresses the problem of estimating the life expectancy function of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan using parametric statistical models. In the study, life expectancy is treated as a positive-valued random variable, and an empirical survival function is constructed based on official demographic data. To describe the mortality process, the Gompertz and Weibull parametric models are employed. The unknown parameters of the models are estimated using the maximum likelihood method. The results demonstrate that the selected parametric models provide a sufficiently good approximation of the empirical life expectancy function and accurately capture the main

characteristics of the mortality process. The findings of the study are of scientific and practical relevance for demographic analysis, as well as for planning insurance and pension systems.

Keywords: life expectancy, parametric models, Gompertz model, Weibull model, demographic forecasting.

Umr davomiyligi funksiyasi (survival function) $S(x)$ ehtimollar nazariyasi, statistik tahlil va aktuar matematikasining asosiy komponentlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Bu funksiya musbat qiymatlarni qabul qiluvchi tasodifiy miqdor T ni, umr davomiyligi yoki beto'xtov ishlash vaqti - x qiymatidan katta bo'lish ehtimolini bildiradi

$$S(x) = P(T > x) = 1 - F(x)$$

umr davomiyligi funksiyasini zichlik funksiyasi orqali ham ifodalash mumkin

$$S(x) = \int_0^{\infty} f(t)dt$$

Umr davomiyligi funksiyasi orqali hazard (xavf) funksiyasi

$$\mu(x) = \frac{f(x)}{S(x)} = -\frac{d}{dx} \ln S(x),$$

kumulativ xavf funksiyasi

$$H(x) = -\ln S(x) = \int_0^x \mu(t)dt,$$

x yoshdagi insonning kutilayotgan qolgan umrining o'rtacha qiymati

$$e_x = \int_0^{\infty} S(x, t)dt$$

kiritiladi. Bu funksiyalar birgalikda umr davomiyligining statistik strukturasi aniqlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Umr davomiyligi funksiyasi sug'urta sohasida keng qo'llaniladi, masalan, hayotni sug'urtalashda $S(x)$ yordamida sug'urta mukofotlari va kompaniya zaxiralari hisoblanadi; pensiya tizimlarida kutilayotgan yashab qolish ehtimolligi asosida pensiya to'lovlari rejasi shakllanadi; umr davomiyligi ortishi bilan bog'liq risklarni prognoz qilishda qo'llaniladi; aholi hayot sifati, umr davomiyligi va farovonlik darajasini o'lchashda asosiy ko'rsatkichlardan biri hisoblanadi, $S(x)$ asosida davlat byudjeti, sog'liqni saqlash va pensiya tizimi uchun zarur prognozlar amalga oshiriladi, e_x (o'rtacha umr davomiyligi) ko'rsatkich pensiya fondlari, hayot sug'urtasi, uzoq muddatli qarzlilar va kreditlar uchun hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga.

Umr davomiyligi funksiyasi $S(x)$ g'oyasi inson umrining statistik, iqtisodiy va demografik modellashtirilishida uzoq tarixga ega. Quyida asosiy bosqichlarni ko'rib o'tamiz. John Graunt (1662) Londondagi o'lim statistikasini yig'ib, birinchi hayot jadvalini yaratgan. U yoshga nisbatan yashab qolish ehtimolligini statistik tarzda ifodalab bergan. Graunt ishlari aholi sog'lig'i, migratsiya va tug'ilishlar haqida birinchi ilmiy kuzatishlar bo'lgan. Edmond Halley (1693) Breslau (hozirgi Vrotslav, Polsha) aholisiga oid o'lim ma'lumotlariga asoslangan to'liq hayot jadvalini yaratgan. U har bir yosh uchun $S(x)$ ni quyidagicha baholagan

$$S(x) = \frac{\textit{Tirik qolganlar soni}}{\textit{Yosh guruhi boshlanishidagi soni}}$$

Bu jadval sug'urta kompaniyalarining ilk matematik vositasiga aylangan. Abraham de Muavr (1725) hayotni chiziqli kamayuvchi ehtimollik modeli sifatida tavsiflagan:

$$S(x) = 1 - \frac{x}{\omega}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq \omega$$

bu yerda ω – maksimal umr (masalan, $\omega = 86$ yil). Modelning soddaligi uni sug'urta va aktuar hisob-kitoblarida qo'llashni osonlashtirgan. Benjamin Gompertz (1825) biologik qarish jarayonini eksponensial o'lim stavkasi bilan ifodalalashni taklif qilgan:

$$\mu(x) = ae^{bx}, \Rightarrow S(x) = \exp\left(-\frac{a}{b}(e^{bx} - 1)\right)$$

Bu model inson umrida yosh ortishi bilan xavfning tezlashishini aks ettiradi. William Makeham (1860) Gompertz modelini kengaytirib, doimiy xavf (background mortality) ni qo'shdi

$$\mu(x) = A + ae^{bx}, \Rightarrow S(x) = \exp\left(-Ax - \frac{a}{b}(e^{bx} - 1)\right)$$

O'zbekiston Respublikasi uchun umr davomiyligi taqsimot funksiyasini baholash uchun yuqorida keltirilgan modellardan hamda 2008 yilda olingan ma'lumotlardan foydalanamiz.

x (yosh)	l_x (aholi soni)	d_x (Vafot etganlar soni)	x yosh	l_x (aholi soni)	d_x (Vafot etganlar soni)
0	100000	1307	50	91336	558
1	98693	263	55	88047	861
5	98194	39	60	82447	1443
10	98034	29	65	73599	1550
15	97879	33	70	62879	2776
20	97638	66	75	47716	2973
25	97230	109	80	30933	2961
30	96608	149	85	17012	1827
35	95801	178	90	6968	851
40	94755	256	95	2782	297
45	93392	339	100	1485	601

1-jadval. O'zbekiston Respublikasi aholisi uchun umr davomiyligi jadvali (2008 yil)

Avval berilgan jadval asosida empirik umr davomiyligi funksiyasini qurib olamiz hamda mazkur empirik umr davomiyligi funksiyasi asosida (ya'ni empirik umr davomiyligi funksiyasiga eng yaqin bo'lgan) ikki hil modelni tanlaymiz. Bular Gomperts modeli va Weibull modellaridan foydalanamiz. Gomperts modeli umumiy holda

$$\mu(x) = A + Be^{Cx}, \quad S(x) = \exp\left(-Ax - \frac{B}{C}(e^{Cx} - 1)\right)$$

formula bilan aniqlanadi. A parametri yoshga bog'liq bo'lmagan tashqi xavflar (masalan, zo'rvonlik yoki keskin kasalliklar)ni, B va C parametrlar biologik qarishning eksponensial tezligini bildiradi.

Weibull modelining umumiy ko'rinishi

$$\mu(x) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1}, \quad S(x) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^\beta\right)$$

Weibull modeli ishonchlilik nazariyasi, sanoat statistikasi va umr davomiyligi tahlilida keng qo'llaniladigan parametrik model hisoblanadi. Bu ikki modelni ko'rinishidan tanlanma bo'yicha noma'lum parametrlarni baholashda aniq analitik yechim olish imkoniyati mavjud emasligini ko'rish mumkin. Shuning uchun noma'lum parametrlarni sonli usullar yordamida baholaymiz.

Weibull modelida parametrlarni baholash. Weibull modelining umr davomiyligi funksiyasi quyidagicha aniqlanadi

$$S(x) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^\beta\right)$$

bu yerda $\alpha > 0$ - masshtab parametri, $\beta > 0$ - shakl parametri. Avval noma'lum parametrlarni haqiqatga maksimal o'xshashlik usuli yordamida baholaymiz. Agar bizda n ta to'liq kuzatilgan tanlanmalar mavjud bo'lsa: x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , u holda haqiqatga o'xshashlik funksiyasi

$$L(\alpha, \beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(x_i) = \prod_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{x_i}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{x_i}{\alpha}\right)^\beta} \right]$$

va uning logarifmi

$$l(\alpha, \beta) = n \ln \beta - n \ln \alpha + (\beta - 1) \sum \ln x_i - \beta \sum \left(\frac{x_i}{\alpha}\right)^\beta$$

bo'ladi. Bu $l(\alpha, \beta)$ funksiyasini noma'lum parametrlar bo'yicha hosilalarini nolga teng qilib yechamiz

$$\frac{\partial l}{\partial \alpha} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial l}{\partial \beta} = 0$$

Bu tenglamalarni analitik yechimini topib bo'lmaydi. Shuning uchun sonli usullardan foydalanib (buning uchun maxsus dasturiy vositalardan foydalanamiz) α va β ni topamiz. Berilgan tanlanma (1-jadval) bo'yicha α va β ning qiymatlari: $\alpha \approx 78.18$ va $\beta \approx 6.23$ bo'ladi.

Gompertz modelida parametrlarni baholash. Gompertz modelining umr davomiyligi funksiyasi quyidagicha aniqlanadi

$$S(x) = \exp\left(-\frac{a}{b}(e^{bx} - 1)\right)$$

bu yerda $a > 0$ bosh xavf intensivligi, $b > 0$ qarish tezligi. Bu modelda ham haqiqatga maksimal o'xshashlik usuli yordamida baholaymiz. Haqiqatga o'xshashlik funksiyasi logarifmining ko'rinishi

$$l(a, b) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\ln a + bx_i - \frac{a}{b} (e^{bx_i} - 1) \right]$$

Bu modelda ham tenglamalarni analitik yechimini topib bo'lmaydi. Shuning uchun sonli usullardan foydalanib noma'lum parametrlarni baholaymiz: $a \approx 0.0001074$ va $b \approx 0.08494$.

Noma'lum parametrlarni baholashda kichik kvadratlar usulidan ham foydalanish mumkin. Bunda modeldagi $S(x, \theta)$ funksiya bilan $\hat{S}(x) = \frac{l_x}{l_0}$ orasidagi farqni minimallashtirish orqali parametrlar aniqlanadi:

$$\min_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^n (S(x_i; \theta) - \hat{S}(x_i))^2$$

Quyida berilgan o'limlik jadvali asosida qurilgan empirik umr davomiyligi funksiyasi va o'rganilgan modellar bo'yicha baholangan umr davomiyligi funksiyalarini solishtirma grafigini chizamiz:

1-rasm. O'zbekiston aholisi umr davomiyligi bo'yicha empirik va parametrik (Weibull, Gompertz) funksiyalarining qiyosiy tahlili

Xulosa

Umr davomiyligi funksiyasi ehtimollar nazariyasi, statistik tahlil va aktuar hisoblarning muhim tushunchalaridan biri bo'lib, sug'urta, pensiya va sog'liqni saqlash tizimlarida ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy prognozlar tuzishda keng qo'llaniladi. Mazkur tadqiqotda O'zbekiston Respublikasi aholisi bo'yicha 2008-yil statistik ma'lumotlari asosida empirik umr davomiyligi funksiyasi Gompertz va Weibull parametrik modellari bilan qiyosiy tahlil qilindi. Natijalar tanlangan modellar empirik funksiyaga yaxshi mos kelishini

ko'rsatib, ularning real demografik jarayonlarni tavsiflashdagi samaradorligini tasdiqlaydi. Gompertz modeli biologik qarish jarayonini hisobga olib, o'lim xavfining yosh ortishi bilan tezlashishini ifodalaydi, Weibull modeli esa xavfning vaqtga bog'liq o'zgarishini moslashuvchan tarzda modellashtirish imkonini beradi.

Parametrlarni baholashda analitik yechimlarning mavjud emasligi sababli, haqiqatga maksimal o'xshashlik (MLE) va kichik kvadratlar (OLS) kabi usullardan foydalangan holda sonli optimizatsiya yondashuvlari qo'llanildi. Tadqiqotda parametrlar maxsus dasturiy vositalar yordamida hisoblab chiqildi va har bir model asosida qurilgan nazariy umr davomiyligi funksiyalari empirik funksiyalar bilan solishtirildi.

Natijalar umr davomiyligini modellashtirish orqali aholi salomatligi, pensiya tizimining barqarorligi va sug'urta risklarini aniqlashda aniq va asosli qarorlar qabul qilish imkonini berishini ko'rsatdi. Ayniqsa, hozirgi davrda O'zbekistonda demografik o'zgarishlar, umr ko'rishning ortishi va iqtisodiy islohotlar fonida bunday modellar strategik rejalashtirish uchun nihoyatda muhim hisoblanadi.

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